

ESHELBY MODELS APPLIED TO WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES: A BENCHMARK STUDY

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SUMMARY: The potential of a new unified micro-mechanical model for textile composites is demonstrated using woven fabric composites as an example. The model is based on Eshelby's transformation concepts, in combination with a classical averaging scheme accounting for reinforcement interactions. To simplify the solution of the basic localization problem, a short fibre equivalent has been used for the yarn segments in the original textile. A Mori-Tanaka scheme, being widely used for short fibre composites with moderate fibre volume fractions, has been compared with a singly embedded self-consistent method, popular in the modeling of granular materials. The present model was originally developed for textile composites with complex fibre architectures like knits, but it is shown here that the model is equally performant for other textiles. After an outline of the geometrical description of woven fabrics, the model predictions are compared with finite element, FGM and cell model predictions, and with experimental data.

KEYWORDS: micro-mechanics, textile reinforcement, Mori-Tanaka method

INTRODUCTION

The growing interest in textiles for large scale application in composite parts naturally raises the need for easy-to-use and efficient CAE tools for predicting and optimising various aspects related to component design, including textile deformability, permeability and finally the thermo-mechanical behaviour of the textile composites. Amongst the most widespread micro-mechanical models for textile composites are mechanics of materials based methods like the Fabric Geometry Model (FGM) on the one hand, and finite element based methods on the other hand.

Orientation averaging methods like FGM have been proven to be highly efficient and versatile, but accordingly they lack accuracy. While FGM predicts in-plane moduli reasonably well for a broad class of textile composites, it has been shown that the model behaves poor for the matrix dominated properties, like in-plane shear and out-of-plane stiffness. Consequently, some authors proposed further modifications to the isostrain approach, resulting in so-called

selective averaging methods (SAM, also known as series-parallel models) or weighted averaging models (WAM), but they are limited to very specific load cases respectively textile types and therefore not generally applicable.

Finite element models have superior accuracy, but the expense of their use is high. Detailed, volumetric unit cell models have been created for a few basic textile structures, but a generalized volumetric approach is not yet feasible. The overall belief is that their use is merely in benchmarking of simplified, but more efficient analytical models. Apart from volumetric models, there exists a class of idealized finite element models including frameworks of beams or trusses, micro-macro approaches and mosaic type models. Due to the idealization involved, accuracy is deflated, and for the voxel type mosaic models convergence of the calculated stress fields is slow.

In between these extrema, a class of models exists based upon Aboudi's method of cells. The method was developed for the prediction of unidirectionally reinforced composites, and is based upon a subpartitioning of the textile unit cell into a regular array of hexahedral subcells. The admissible stress fields in each cell are limited to the set of stress fields satisfying continuity conditions across the subcell boundaries. A unique stress field distribution is obtained by minimization of the total complementary energy. The model has been extended towards 2D woven fabric composites by Vandeurzen [1], using a multi-level decomposition scheme to break down the woven fabric unit cell into subcells containing either matrix or yarns. The model is however not easily extended towards complex textiles with an intrinsic 3D yarn architecture (knits, 3D weaves and braids), unless some voxel subpartitioning method is used, like the ones proposed by Gowayed et. al [2], and later on by Bigaud and Hamelin [3]. Nevertheless, to reach reasonable resolution a huge number of subcell divisions would quickly be required, and the model loses its efficiency.

In the present paper, a new micro-mechanical modeling approach for textile composites is presented which is based upon Eshelby's concepts. The principal aim was to develop a unified modeling strategy, applicable to a broad class of textiles. An additional concern was the efficiency of the model, allowing it to be used on a material module level in a global structural analysis code like finite elements. Finally, the model should be an improvement over the classical averaging models by systematically taking into account more geometrical details of the microstructure. In fact, the model was developed originally for knitted fabric composites, for which available models in literature were, and still are sparse. Previously, the potential of the Eshelby models for knitted fabric composites have been demonstrated [4]; it is shown here that the concept equally works for regular textiles like weaves.

A unified modeling strategy starts with a unified geometrical model. Therefore, some words are spent to the specific geometrical description of weaves that has been adopted throughout. Afterwards, the essentials of the mechanical model are briefly reformulated. As a first application, the model is compared with FGM and finite elements, showing that the out-of-plane performance of the new model is significantly improved with respect to the classical FGM. Finally, the elastic constants of a series of practical woven fabric composites are predicted and compared with experimental data and with the complementary energy model. It will be shown that even for hybrid fabrics and more exotic steel fabrics the model performs equally well.

MODEL DESCRIPTION

Geometry of woven fabrics

Many geometrical models of woven fabrics available in literature are based on the use of special shape functions for the description of the yarn paths, including arcs, sine functions and straight sections. In the present work, spline functions with C^2 -continuity have been used throughout. Splines are more flexible in use, and allow to decouple the formalism used in the micro-mechanical model from the specific derivation of the splines for a particular textile type.

The starting point of the geometrical analysis of woven fabric composites is the checkerboard representation describing the yarn interlacing pattern (Fig. 1). In most applications, a single yarn type is used for warp and fill directions, but hybrid fabrics are equally possible. Hence, to account for these hybrid fabrics an additional row and column is added to the checkerboard matrix, specifying the warp and fill yarn types for each row resp. column in the weave pattern.

Fig. 1: Checkerboard matrix representation of a 2D weave structure

Each yarn in the woven fabric unit cell is split up into a number of elementary bent intervals between two consecutive interlacing points. The number of bent intervals in warp and fill directions equals the number of rows and columns of the interlacing pattern. Each bent interval is mathematically represented by a cubic spline section in the form of (Fig. 2):

$$x_i(W, u) = a_i u^3 + b_i u^2 + c_i u + d_i \quad (i=1,3) \quad (1)$$

The coefficients in Eqn 1 are determined by applying suitable boundary conditions at the end points of the interval (Fig. 2). Firstly, the co-ordinates of these points can be calculated from the known yarn spacings in warp and fill directions, and from the measured yarn crimps. Secondly, the tangent vectors at the cross-over points ly parallel to the fabric plane. Finally, heartline curvatures at the end-points are calculated from the yarn cross-sectional shapes and the assumption of perfect contact in the cross-over region.

It can easily be shown that these conditions are sufficient and define uniquely the shape of the bent interval. Note further that a similar procedure can be used for the on-axis geometrical description of the yarn paths in biaxial braids. For braids an additional step is required, in which the obtained on-axis spline coefficients (Eqn 1) are transformed into the global coordinate system using the rules for first order tensor transformations.

Fig. 2: Bent interval of a warp yarn W running between two fill yarns F and F^* in a woven fabric. Definition of essential geometrical parameters.

Micro-mechanical Model

A detailed discussion of the mechanical model used in the present paper can be found in [4], where the model was applied to warp knitted fabric composites. In the following, only the main principles are resumed.

The different yarn sections in the unit cell are subdivided into a number of smaller segments, where each yarn segment is geometrically characterised by its total volume fraction, spatial orientation, cross-sectional aspect ratio and local curvature. Apart from the (measured) cross-sectional yarn shape, these quantities are easily calculated from the description of the yarn bent intervals (Eqn 1). The stress state in the segments is approximated by a piecewise constant stress distribution. Next, Eshelby's equivalent inclusion principle is adopted to transform each heterogenous yarn segment into a homogeneity with a fictitious transformation strain distribution. Although the heterogenous problem is reduced to a localisation problem in a homogenous medium by this transformation, the computation of the perturbed stress field still remains a complex task due to (1) the complexity of the yarn geometry itself and (2) the large amount of inter-yarn interactions.

In [5] a numerical solution method is proposed based upon the work of Pijaudier-Cabot and Bazant [6], but the model solution time and required resources increase considerably with the number of segments within the textile unit cell.

A more efficient alternative that was also proposed in [4] makes use of a short fibre equivalent, which physically reflects the drop in the axial load carrying capability of a curved yarn with respect to an initially straight yarn. Every yarn segment is hence linked to an equivalent short fibre, possessing an identical cross-sectional shape, volume fraction and orientation as the original segment it is derived from. The length of the equivalent fibre on the other hand is related to the curvature of the original yarn. For textiles with smoothly varying curvature radii (e.g. excluding idealised stitch loops found in non-crimp fabric preforms), a proportional relationship between the short fibre length and the local yarn curvature radius is the most straightforward choice and sufficiently accurate for the present purpose. The major advantage of the exploited equivalency is that the determination of the stress field in a short fibre (which can be approximated by an ellipsoid), embedded in an infinite matrix (the dilute suspension), is well known and can be obtained through Eshelby's tensor.

The interaction problem between the different reinforcing yarns is solved in the traditional way, by averaging out the image stress sampling over the different phases. If a Mori-Tanaka scheme is used, the stiffness tensor \mathbf{C}^C of the composite is hence obtained as:

$$\mathbf{C}^C = \left[c_m \mathbf{C}^m + \langle c_s \mathbf{C}^s \mathbf{A}^s \rangle \right] \left[c_m \mathbf{I} + \langle c_s \mathbf{A}^s \rangle \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where the subscripts m and s denote the matrix and a yarn segment respectively, c_i is the volume fraction of phase i ($i = m, s$), and the angle brackets denote a configurational average. The tensor \mathbf{A}^s is the localisation tensor for segment s , and is given by:

$$\mathbf{A}^s = \left[\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{S}^s \mathbf{C}^{m-1} (\mathbf{C}^s - \mathbf{C}^m) \right]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

The Eshelby tensor \mathbf{S}^s in Eqn 3 depends upon the shape of the equivalent short fibre representing the yarn segment, and the properties of the matrix. If the matrix is isotropic, a valid assumption for most practical polymer matrices, the Eshelby tensor is conveniently calculated.

In the modelling of the mechanical behaviour of granular type materials, like polycrystals, the self-consistent method proved to be more useful. For unidirectionally reinforced composites with a soft matrix, the self-consistent method performs poorly in the prediction of transverse, matrix dominated properties. However, this deficit largely disappears as the differences in matrix deformation constraint over the spatial orientations is leveled out, like in multi-oriented textile composites with inherently stable fabric preforms. Using the self-consistent approach, the composite stiffness is given by:

$$\mathbf{C}^C = c_m \mathbf{C}^m + \langle c_s (\mathbf{C}^s - \mathbf{C}^m) \mathbf{A}^s \rangle \quad (4)$$

The segment localisation tensor for the self-consistent method is similar as in Eqn 3, except for the matrix stiffness which is now replaced by the (unknown) composite stiffness. The same holds for the Eshelby tensor; as most textile composites are anisotropic in their mechanical behaviour, the Eshelby tensor can consequently only be evaluated by numerical means. Furthermore, Eqn 4 represents an implicit equation from which the composite stiffness has to be solved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Parametrical Study

A first series of model predictions has been performed on a woven fabric model that has been published by Paumelle [7], who investigated the importance of the constituent properties and the fabric geometry on the overall composite performance. Paumelle used a finite element model of the fabric unit cell to predict the elastic properties. His results have been chosen as a reference solution, as also out-of-plane predictions were reported. Out-of-plane properties are difficult to assess experimentally, while discrepancies in different micro-mechanical models, especially the orientation averaging methods, are mostly pronounced in the out-of-plane behaviour.

The fabric is a balanced plain weave with equal yarn spacings in the warp and fill directions. Each yarn consists of 415 fibres with a diameter of 0.01 mm. The yarn flattening, defined as the ratio of the major axis to the minor axis of the yarn cross-section, was fixed to 6 and the fibre packing inside the yarn was set to 81%. In the parametrical calculations, the fibre modulus was varied between 40 and 90 GPa, and the resin modulus between 1 and 8 GPa. The yarn spacing in warp and fill directions, affecting the overall fibre volume fraction, was changed between 0.62 and 1.40 mm.

Fig. 3: Out-of-plane Young's modulus predictions: FEM, FGM-NX-P (iso-strain), Mori-Tanaka (FC-MT) and self-consistent (FC-SC) models.

Fig. 3 compares the out-of-plane modulus predictions with the finite element data from Paumelle. Also indicated on this figure are the predictions from the FGM. Although the in-plane predictions from the latter model agree well with the finite element results, the out-of-plane modulus is clearly overestimated. The differences between the Mori-Tanaka and self-consistent predictions are small and relatively constant over the fibre volume fraction range 20-50%. Both models yield results that are close to finite element predictions. For knitted fabrics, the difference increases with higher volume fractions. This indicates that woven fabric composites behave more like granular materials compared to knitted fabric composites.

Fig. 4: Out-of-plane shear modulus predictions: FEM, FGM-NX-P (iso-strain), Mori-Tanaka (FC-MT) and self-consistent (FC-SC) models.

Similar tendencies can be observed for the out-of-plane shear modulus (Fig. 4). In fact, the FGM predicts an out-of-plane shear modulus which is always higher than the in-plane shear modulus, while the finite element calculations show the opposite. This is also observed for the present inclusion models, which again are in good correlation with the finite element data.

Experimental Validation

The inclusion models were further validated against experimental data for a broad range of weave types and materials, the characteristics of which are listed in Table 1. The fabrics Mesh 40 and Mesh 48 are steel monofilament fabrics. Due to the isotropy of the reinforcement, properties predicted using weighting methods such as FGM would be in huge error. The unit cells of all weaves were subdivided into a total of 100 yarn segments, except for the basket weave RE280 and the hybrid twill weave 1161, which were approximated by 200 segments. Typical calculation times on a Sun Ultrasparc 2 workstation are about 0.1 sec for the Mori-Tanaka method and 50 sec for the iterative self-consistent method.

Table 1: Woven fabric types and geometry parameters used in the experimental validation. V_p refers to the fibre packing, while V_f denotes the global fibre volume fraction in the composite; f is the yarn flattening, p the yarn spacing and h the yarn crimp.

#	Fabric	Pattern	Mat	Tex (g/km)	V_p (%)	f	p (mm)	h (mm)	V_f (%)	
1	R420L		W	E-glass	610	75.0	12.1	2.59	-	32.5
			F	E-glass	610	75.0	10.0	2.95	0.14	
2	R420H		W	E-glass	610	75.0	12.0	2.72	-	49.5
			F	E-glass	610	75.0	11.5	2.94	0.14	
3	R330L		W	E-glass	480	75.0	13.4	2.69	-	36.8
			F	E-glass	480	75.0	13.9	3.07	0.14	
4	R330H		W	E-glass	480	75.0	14.0	2.77	-	44.7
			F	E-glass	480	75.0	13.0	3.07	0.14	
5	RE280L		W	E-glass	320	75.0	17.1	2.22	-	33.7
			F	E-glass	320	75.0	21.4	2.35	0.14	
6	RE280H		W	E-glass	320	75.0	18.0	2.22	-	42.7
			F	E-glass	320	75.0	20.0	2.35	0.14	
7	1151		W	Carbon	na	70.0	9.0	2.00	-	33.0
			F	Kevlar®	na	70.0	8.5	2.00	0.16	
8	1161		W	E-glass	na	72.0	5.0	1.336	-	37.0
			W*	Kevlar®	na	72.0	5.6	1.336	-	
			F	E-glass	na	72.0	5.0	1.336	0.22	
			F*	Kevlar®	na	72.0	5.6	1.336	-	
9	Mesh 40		W	Steel	$d=0.25$	100.0	1.0	0.65	0.15	32.0
			F	Steel		100.0	1.0	0.65	0.35	
10	Mesh 48		W	Steel	$d=0.125$	100.0	1.0	0.525	0.125	19.0
			F	Steel		100.0	1.0	0.525	0.125	

Table 2 compares the experimental in-plane tensile and shear moduli with the Mori-Tanaka and self-consistent predictions. There is generally a good agreement in experimental and model data, also for the hybrid fabrics and the monofilament steel fabrics. For the multi-filament (yarn) fabrics, an FGM model has comparable accuracy as far as the in-plane predictions are concerned. As shown in the previous section, FGM differs substantially with more elaborate models in the out-of-plane property predictions. Even more important is the fact that FGM is not capable of handling the monofilament fabrics Mesh 40 and Mesh 48, due

to the isotropic behaviour of the reinforcement. From Table 2, it is clear that the present inclusion models do not show this deficiency.

Table 2: Comparison of predicted in-plane elastic constants using Mori-Tanaka (MT) and the self-consistent (SC) method with experimental data. All items in GPa.

Fabric	E_{WARP}			E_{FILL}			G		
	Exp	MT	SC	Exp	MT	SC	Exp	MT	SC
R420L	16.53	17.12	17.31	16.93	16.22	16.33	3.67	2.85	3.03
R420H	22.47	25.19	24.83	21.35	24.56	24.00	4.59	4.00	4.23
R330L	19.96	19.60	19.52	18.70	18.23	18.20	3.82	3.18	3.36
R330H	25.67	23.38	23.01	22.46	22.06	21.75	4.36	3.71	3.91
RE280L	17.32	16.81	17.85	16.71	16.81	17.23	3.20	2.79	3.19
RE280H	20.73	22.18	21.89	18.68	21.29	21.12	4.03	3.65	3.81
1151	36.62	31.73	35.56	22.90	23.92	24.48	1.89	1.84	1.88
1161	21.45	19.83	21.00	21.35	20.03	21.16	2.56	2.12	2.26
Mesh 40	28.17	22.94	32.62	15.80	11.84	15.46	2.21	2.05	3.67
Mesh 48	16.40	16.71	19.36	16.50	16.71	19.36	1.48	1.57	1.91

The performance of the present model was further compared with an energetic model based on Aboudi's method of cells, which has been extended to handle woven fabric composites by Vandeurzen [1].

Fig. 5: Polar E-Modulus (a) and G-Modulus (b) Predictions for the E-glass/epoxy fabric RE280L.

Fig. 5 show a polar diagram of the in-plane stiffness constants comparing the current models with the cell model (CEM) for the glass/epoxy fabric RE280. In general, as the CEM model takes into account more detailed geometrical features than the present inclusion models (more precisely the spatial locations of the constituents), it is slightly more accurate. This becomes also clear from polar plots of one of the steel fabrics (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Polar E-Modulus (a) and G-Modulus (b) Predictions for the Steel/epoxy Fabric MESH48.

CONCLUSIONS

A new micro-mechanics approach for textile composites based on Eshelby's concepts has been presented. The model bridges the gap between easy-to-use but less accurate orientation averaging models and the more detailed but inefficient finite element based models.

The potential of the present method has been demonstrated on woven fabric composites. The fabric geometry has been modelled using generic spline functions, allowing for a unified description of different textile classes.

Based upon finite element benchmarks and experimental data it has been shown that the Eshelby methods are superior to isostrain models, and that they approach the accuracy of the complementary energy model, which is of comparable efficiency when applied to woven fabric composites. However, the energy models are not easily extended to complex textile geometries, whereas the present model provides a truly unified approach.

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REFERENCES

1. P. Vandeurzen, J. Ivens, I. Verpoest, "Micro-stress Analysis of Woven Fabric Composites by Multilevel Decomposition", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 32, No. 7, 1998, pp. 623-651.
2. Y.A. Gowayed, C. Pastore, C.S. Howart, "Modification and Application of a Unit Cell Continuum Model to Predict the Elastic Properties of Textile Composites", *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 27, No. 2, pp. 149-155.

3. D. Bigaud, P. Hamelin, “Mechanical Properties Prediction of Textile-reinforced Composite Materials using a Multiscale Energetic Approach”, *Composite Structures*, Vol. 38, No. 1-4, pp. 361-371.
4. G. Huysmans, I. Verpoest, P. Van Houtte “A Poly-Inclusion Approach for the Elastic Modelling of Knitted Fabric Composites”, *Acta Materiala*, Vol. 46, No. 9, 1998, pp. 3003-3013.
5. G. Huysmans, I. Verpoest, P. Van Houtte “A novel Mori-Tanaka Method for Textile Composites with Continuous Fibres”, *In preparation*.
6. G. Pijaudier-Cabot, Z.P. Bazant, “Cracks interacting with Particles or Fibres in Composite Materials”, *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, Vol. 117, No. 7, 1996, pp. 1611-1630.
7. Paumelle, A. Hassim, F. Léné, “Microstress Analysis in Woven Composite Structures”, *La recherche aérospatiale*, No. 6, 1990, pp. 47-62.